

Exploring pilot scale ultrasound-microwave assisted extraction of organic acids and phytochemicals from brown seaweed *Alaria esculenta*

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates ultrasound (US) and microwave (MW) technologies – both applied individually (ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE), microwave-assisted extraction (MAE)) and simultaneously (ultrasound–microwave-assisted extraction (UMAE)) for extracting bioactive compounds from a brown seaweed *Alaria esculenta*. This research emphasizes sustainability by using wet biomass and water for extraction. Employing a range of power (336–1340 W (MW); 50–200 W (US)) and time (5–20 min) conditions, the study evaluates multiple phytochemicals as well as antioxidant activities in the obtained extracts. The highest total soluble carbohydrate contents (32.68 mg glucose equivalents (GE)/100 mg extract) were achieved by UAE (200 W, 20 min). UMAE (50 W (US), 1340 W (MW), 10 min) had the highest levels of total phenolic contents (2.07 mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/100 mg extract) and FRAP (38.36 μM Trolox equivalents (TE)/mg extract). The highest protein content (15.62 ± 1.69 bovine serum albumin equivalents (BSAE) mg/100 mg extract) was recorded by UMAE (100 W (US), 1340 W (MW), 20 min). MAE (1340 W, 20 min) achieved the highest levels of succinic (7.52 mg/g extract) and lactic acids (39.08 mg/g extract), while UMAE (670 W (MW), 100 W (US), 5 min) extracted the highest amounts of malic (3.02 mg/g extract) and α-ketoglutaric acids (2.41 mg/g extract). Lactic acid, followed by pyruvic acid was the major organic acid present in the extracts. Scanning electron microscopy images confirmed increased cell damage in the biomass by all the treatments, with higher levels of surface roughness and enlarged pores appreciated after UMAE. Hence, this work being among the first to demonstrate US and MW application, both individually and simultaneously, on *Alaria esculenta*, utilizing an integrated commercially available pilot-scale system and a green extraction solvent, sheds light on the extraction of valuable phytochemicals including underexplored organic acids which hold immense potential for diverse applications.

1. Introduction

In 2020, global algae production reached 36 million tons (wet weight), with aquaculture contributing 97 % and wild harvesting the remaining 3 % [1]. Macroalgae or seaweed farming industry, valued at USD 5.9 billion in 2019, is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9.1 % until 2027 [2]. By 2030, emerging seaweed markets could reach an estimated value of USD 11.8 billion, according to a recent World Bank report [3]. Seaweeds have been consumed as a part of the diet for ages in Asian and South East Asian countries, such as

China, Japan and Korea, and a few South American countries [4]. In contrast, most of the Western part of the world and European countries have mainly utilised algae to derive gelling agents and colloids for the food industry [4]. Macroalgae grow and thrive in extremely harsh environmental conditions in seas and oceans, whether wild or aquacultured. In order to withstand and defend themselves from such biotic and abiotic stresses, seaweeds produce several metabolites that demonstrate a huge range of bioactivity [5]. However, the production of these metabolites by macroalgae is influenced by various factors affecting the biomass, including meteorological conditions, light

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exposure, salinity, harvest season, maturity at harvest, species and phylogenetic diversity [6]. Among all these compounds carbohydrates, protein and phenolic compounds are gaining wide-popularity due to their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic, anti-diabetic and antioxidant properties [7,8]. To use these valuable compounds for myriad applications, either independently or through incorporation into different food matrices, their efficient extraction from the algal biomass into concentrated forms is a primary necessity. Macroalgae are structurally extremely robust having a complex cell wall structure rich in rigid and viscous polysaccharides that hinder the extractability of intracellular or bound components [9].

Conventional chemical-based extraction methods involve using large quantities of harsh solvents that can leave residues in the extracts. Also, these methods may need high temperatures and long processing times, which increase their energy requirements [10–12]. To overcome these challenges, emerging disruptive technologies have paved the way towards greener extraction methods. These techniques in comparison to the conventional methods, provide higher extract yields by disrupting the aforementioned rigid polysaccharide cell wall network, consuming lesser process run time, without any requirement of additional heating or use of harsh solvents, which in turn enable a clean and green label status of the extracts having retained bioactivity [13,14]. Among these methodologies, novel technologies such as ultrasound (US) and microwave (MW) in individual and combined modes of application have been recently explored to extract multiple bioactive compounds from dried pulverised macroalgae [15,16].

Among the 3 different varieties of seaweeds (red, green and brown) found, brown macroalgae or Phaeophyceae, are the largest in size and are widely harvested along the Irish coast. One such brown macroalgae species is *Alaria esculenta*, commonly known as Atlantic wakame/dabberlocks/badderlocks/winged kelp that can grow up to 4 m long and 25 cm wide. These are regularly consumed along the North Atlantic, North Sea to the North Pacific coastline and are being marketed in its dried form by a handful of algae-based companies as rich sources of fibre, minerals and vitamins. *A. esculenta* has been investigated for its biochemical profile as well for extraction of phytochemicals [17–20]. However, all these studies use *A. esculenta* in its dried and milled form as the raw material for extraction, due to their higher shelf life, stability, greater uniformity, and ease of transportation and handling compared to minimally processed macroalgae. However, using fresh macroalgae can be beneficial, reducing the cost and time of drying and reducing the time needed for re-hydration in advance of the extraction processes.

This study focuses on employing a hybrid US-MW technology using a commercially available integrated extractor equipment to extract phytochemicals and nutrients from fresh *A. esculenta* using water as a green extraction solvent. Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) is based on the application of US resulting in high extraction yields. The mechanism of US extraction is based on the physical effects of acoustic cavitation (sono-physical effect) derived from the implosion of the US induced cavitation bubbles generating turbulence, shock waves and strong shear forces which cause fragmentation and detexturization of the macroalgal cell wall leading to surface erosion and sonoporation, and formation of deep micropits and channels in the cell [21]. All these ultimately result in hydration, swelling, and cell disruption [21]. On the other hand, microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) utilises dielectric heating to convert electromagnetic energy into thermal energy. Dielectric heating works on the mechanism of dipolar and interfacial polarization effects. The electric field component of MW causes dipolar polarization, characterized by rotation and alignment of polar molecules (e.g. water) in both permanent and induced dipoles [22]. Kinetic energy associated with the dipolar molecules' vibrational, rotational and translational movement generates substantial internal thermal energy. Thermal energy is also believed to be dissipated through the interfacial polarization effect, which is viewed as a combination of conduction and dipolar polarization [22]. This thermal energy promotes the diffusional transfer of extraction solvent into the cell matrix, helping in extraction of the

phytochemicals [23].

Apart from aiding in extraction, US has gained significant attention in the food industry in recent times for applications in drying, freezing, cleaning, enzyme inactivation, pasteurization, emulsification and filtration processes [24], while MW has shown prowess in thawing, drying, frying, blanching and pasteurization operations [25]. While scientists have long investigated the individual use of ultrasound and microwave technologies and more recently their sequential application in different food processing operations – their simultaneous application for bioactive extraction remains relatively underexplored and warrants further investigation. This is likely due to the complexities involved in designing suitable equipment, managing its operation and controlling the combined impact of US and MW on the quality of the food constituents [26]. The simultaneous application of US and MW via ultrasound–microwave-assisted extraction (UMAE) has been scarcely explored in fresh macroalgae, and it has been hypothesized that this technology can harness the synergistic effects of US and MW forces and improve extraction yields [15]. Researchers have also advocated that their synergistic application accounts for shorter and energy-efficient extraction processes [26]. Therefore, this study aims to explore the use of ultrasound (US) and microwave (MW) technologies – applied both individually (ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE), microwave-assisted extraction (MAE)) and simultaneously (ultrasound–microwave-assisted extraction (UMAE)) - under multiple power (336–1340 W (UMAE); 50–200 W (US)) and time (5–20 min) conditions, for the extraction of phytochemicals (total phenolic compounds, protein and total soluble carbohydrates), organic acids and antioxidant activities (DPPH and FRAP) from *A. esculenta*, increasing the sustainability of the processes by using wet raw biomass and water as extraction solvent. The surface morphology of selected macroalgal biomass residues post-extraction was also explored to elucidate the physical cell disruptive potential of these techniques. Simultaneous US and MW application to extract phytochemicals although investigated in recent years, were applied mostly by connecting individual US and MW equipments together [27,28] unlike the use of a marketed integrated US-MW integrated extractor in our study. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that utilises a commercially available pilot-scale integrated US-MW system and a green solvent to extract phytochemicals including rarely studied organic acids from fresh or wet biomass of *A. esculenta*.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Biomass processing and chemical reagents

Cultivated brown seaweed or macroalgae *A. esculenta* harvested in March 2020 was purchased from Dúrla Seaweed (Co. Mayo, Ireland). The fresh biomass was washed thoroughly with water to remove epiphytes and free surface water was removed with tissue paper. The biomass was cut using a TC11 chopper (Myers, Cork, Ireland), until approximately 0.5 cm in length. The fresh macroalgae was vacuum packed and stored at -20°C . The dry matter content of the fresh samples was determined by oven-drying the samples (105°C , 16 h) following the official analysis methods described by the AOAC 942.05 [29]. All chemical reagents used in this study were of analytical grade and purchased from Merck (Sigma Aldrich), Ireland. Ultrapure water (Milli-Q® Direct 8 Water Purification System, Millipore SAS67120, Molsheim, France) was used for all extraction processes and analyses.

2.2. Extraction procedures

Macroalgal biomass was mixed with ultrapure water at a dilution ratio of seaweed:water of 1:10 (w/v), and the samples were then extracted either by microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE), and ultrasound-microwave-assisted extraction (UMAE). All technological treatments were performed using an E200 equipment (IDCO SAS, Marseille, France) (Fig. 1B) consisting of a

Fig. 1. (A) Process flow for the generation of macroalgal extracts by microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) and ultrasound-microwave-assisted extraction (UMAE) (B) E200 equipment for MAE, UAE and UMAE.

cylindrical sample vessel (volume: 0.5 to 6 L) fitted with a rotary stirrer and an US transducer (25 kHz, 0–200 W) at its bottom wall, connected horizontally to a MW generator (2 kW/2450 MHz with adjustable power 300–1950 W). The experimental design followed in this study is schematically represented in Fig. 1A. The combinations of MW, US power with processing time of the three modes of extraction (MAE, UAE and UMAE) are provided in Table S1.

The prepared macroalgal-water mixtures were loaded in the sample vessel with continuous stirring (50 rpm). The impact of the US and MW was investigated at their low, medium and high power settings of the US-MW extractor by adjusting the level to 25 %, 50 % and 100 % of the maximum applicable power. The maximum power level was set to 100 % and then levelled down by 50 % reduction each time to set the medium and low power levels, hence 50 and 25 %. So, depending on the volume treated in each experiment (1250 mL), the power applied in case of MW applications translated to 336 W (25 % or low), 670 W (50 % or medium) and 1340 W (100 % or high). Similarly, for the US application, its power levels translated to 50 W (25 % or low), 100 W (50 % or medium) and 200 W (100 % or high). So the 3 modes of technologies were applied as following: MAE (336, 670 and 1340 W), UAE (50, 100 and 200 W) and UMAE (all possible combinations of the aforementioned US and MW power levels, simultaneously). All the technological treatments were performed for 5, 10 and 20 min, resulting in a total of 45 runs covering UAE, MAE and UMAE. The ranges of temperature as measured by the temperature sensor at the top/bottom of the extraction vessel were as follows: before extraction for all treatments: (16/16–23/24 °C) and after extraction: MAE (25/35–90/71 °C), UAE (22/22–30/39 °C) and UMAE (26/28–110/107 °C). Following the extraction treatments, the mixtures were filtered, and each liquid filtrate was collected, freeze-dried (FD) (FD80 model 119, Cuddon Engineering, Blenheim, New Zealand), packed air-tight in sealed plastic tubes (Falcon™, Fischer Scientific, UK) and stored at –20 °C until further analysis.

The yields of the extracts were determined following the equation below:

$$\text{Extract yield (g/100 g dry macroalgae)} = \frac{\text{Weight of FD extract (g) / Volume of liquid filtrate (mL)}}{\text{Weight of macroalgae (g)}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.3. Chemical analyses of the extracts

2.3.1. Total phenolic content (TPC)

The FD extract powders were dispersed in water (2 mg/mL) and vigorously mixed in a vortex shaker. The mixture was centrifuged at 10000g for 10 min and the supernatants were collected as the sample extracts. TPC was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent as described by Ganesan, Kumar and Bhaskar [30] with slight modifications. Briefly, 100 µL of the sample extracts (2 mg/mL) and gallic acid standards (0–0.5 mg/mL) were mixed with 2 mL of 2 % (w/v) solution of sodium carbonate and mixed thoroughly before adding 100 µL of 1 M Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. The mixtures were incubated in dark conditions for 30 min at room temperature and the absorbance was read at 720 nm using a BioTek Epoch 2 (Agilent Technologies, CA, USA) spectrophotometer. TPC results were expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per 100 mg dried extract. The standard curve of gallic acid for estimation of TPC is provided in Fig. S1.

2.3.2. Protein content

Protein contents of the extracts were determined using the Pierce™ Bicinchoninic acid (BCA) Protein Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Illinois, USA) complying with the manufacturer's recommendations as also followed in several studies [31–33]. Briefly, 25 µL of bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard (0–2 mg/mL) and sample extracts (2 mg/mL) prepared in a similar way as in 2.3.1., were mixed with 200 µL of the BCA working reagent (50:1, Reagent A (mix of sodium carbonate, sodium bicarbonate, bicinchoninic acid and sodium tartrate in 0.1 M sodium hydroxide): Reagent B (4 % cupric sulfate)). The solutions were agitated thoroughly for 30 s, incubated (37 °C, 30 min) and cooled to room temperature. The absorbance of the reactions was measured at 562 nm using a BioTek Epoch 2 (Agilent Technologies, CA, USA) spectrophotometer. Protein content values were expressed as mg BSA equivalents (BSAE)/100 mg dried extract. Standard curve of BSA for estimation of protein content is represented in Fig. S2.

2.3.3. Total soluble carbohydrates (TSC) content

TSC was analysed using the phenol-sulfuric acid method with the modifications described by Masuko, Minami, Iwasaki, Majima, Nishimura and Lee [34]. Briefly, 30 µL of sample extract (2 mg/mL) and D-glucose standard (0–50 mg/mL) were mixed with 150 µL of concentrated sulfuric acid. The reactions were mixed for 2 min, followed by adding 30 µL of a 5 % (w/v) phenol solution. The reactions were

incubated in a water bath (90 °C, 5 min), cooled to room temperature and read at 490 nm in a spectrophotometer (BioTek Epoch 2, Agilent Technologies, CA, USA). TSC values were expressed as mg glucose equivalents (GE) per 100 mg dried extract. Standard curve of D-glucose for TSC is provided in Fig. S3.

$$\text{DPPH (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Absorbance blank} - \text{Absorbance samples or positive control})}{\text{Absorbance blank}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

2.3.4. Organic acids profiling

The authors selected 2 extracts each from MAE, UAE and UMAE from the conditions resulting in the lowest and highest TSC values to obtain the organic acid profile, considering that organic acids are mostly co-extracted with soluble carbohydrates as seen in previous studies [35–39]. Extraction of organic acid was conducted based on the method of Kelebek and Selli [40], wherein samples were dissolved in distilled water (sample:water ratio 1:5) for 30 min at room temperature and the resultant extracts were centrifuged (12,000g, 7 min) and filtered through 0.45 µm filter (Millipore™, Merck) before injection [41]. Determinations were performed in an Agilent 1260 model equipped with an Aminex HPX-87H column (300 × 7.8 mm) (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA) at 40 °C and an isocratic elution (water/formic acid; 99.9:0.1; v/v) at a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min, with 10 µL of injection volume. The organic acids were identified by UV spectra against standards using retention times and confirmed using liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS, Agilent 6430) with electrospray ionization (ESI). Negative ion mode was applied with the following parameters: drying gas of N₂ at flow rate of 12 L/min, drying gas temperature of 200 °C, capillary voltage of 3000 V, and nebulizer pressure of 50 psi [42]. Data gaining was established with multiple reactions monitoring (MRM), which especially identifies specific mass transitions in MS-MS negative ion mode at pre-set retention times [42]. Calibration curves of the standard organic acids were used to quantify the organic acids. The calibration curves of the standard organic acids and the LC-MS/MS chromatogram of the extracts- counts (%) versus acquisition time (min) are provided in Figs. S4 and S5, respectively.

2.4. Antioxidant activity measurement

2.4.1. Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP)

FRAP was performed as indicated by Bolanos de la Torre, Henderson, Nigam and Owusu-Apenten [43]. FRAP working solution was prepared using acetate buffer (300 mM, pH 3.6), ferric chloride solution (20 mM), 2,4,6-Tripyridyl-s-Triazine (TPTZ) (10 mM in 40 mM HCl) and water at ratio 10:1:1:1.4 (v/v/v/v). The reaction was started by mixing 280 µL of FRAP working solution and 20 µL of sample extracts (2 mg/mL) or trolox standard (15–105 µM). The mixtures were incubated (30 min, 37 °C, dark conditions) and the absorbance of the reactions was read at 593 nm (BioTek Epoch 2, Agilent Technologies, CA, USA). The FRAP antioxidant activity of each extract is expressed as µM Trolox equivalents (TE) per mg of dried extract. Standard curve of trolox is provided in Fig. S6.

2.4.2. 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging activity

DPPH radical scavenging activity was performed according to the method described by Nicklisch and Waite [44] with slight modifications. Briefly, freeze-dried extracts and positive control (ascorbic acid) were diluted to 1 mg/mL in citrate phosphate buffer (pH 5) containing 0.3 % (v/v) of Triton X-100. 190 µL of the citrate-phosphate buffer alone (blank), ascorbic acid, and samples were mixed with 10 µL of a 2 mM methanolic DPPH solution and the reactions were incubated for 30 min (room temperature, dark condition). The absorbance of the reactions

before and after the addition of DPPH solution was monitored at 515 nm in a spectrophotometer (BioTek Epoch 2, Agilent Technologies, CA, USA). The DPPH inhibitory activity or DPPH (%) was calculated using the equation described below.

2.5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface characteristics of the untreated macroalgal sample (fresh *A. esculenta*) and 3 macroalgal residues post-extraction using different extraction technologies (MAE, UAE and UMAE) were analysed by SEM following the method adapted by Suchintita Das, Zhu, Hannon, Mullins, Alves, Garcia-Vaquero and Tiwari [14] with few modifications. All macroalgal residues following extraction were freeze-dried, placed on stubs and coated with a 5 nm layer of gold using a peltier cooled sputter coating unit (Emitech K575X, Quorum Technologies, UK). The images were recorded using a Regulus 8230 (Hitachi Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) scanning electron microscope.

2.6. Statistical analyses

Yield of extracts were measured in duplicate. All the chemical analyses were performed in duplicate and spectrophotometric readings of the duplicate were taken in triplicate. Chromatographic analyses were carried out in triplicate. The influence of MW power, US power and extraction time on extract yield, TPC, protein content, TSC, organic acid composition, and associated antioxidant activities were analysed using a one-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA). Tukey test was used to differentiate between means (95 % confidence, $p < 0.05$) in SPSS version 23.0. The correlations in the data were explored using R version 4.3.2 [45]. “ggplot2” and “corrplot” were used to generate the Pearson's correlation matrix [46] and “cor.mtest” was used to generate the p -values within the correlation matrix. The variance within the full data was further explored by principal component analysis (PCA) using Varimax rotation with Kaiser normalisation to extract the eigenvalues values of the components using SPSS version 23.0.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Extraction yields

The yields of extract achieved using MAE at multiple MW power (336–1340 W) and extraction time (5–20 min) are represented in Fig. 2A. There is a pattern indicating an increased extract yield with an increase of MW power from 336 to 670 W to 1340 W when applied for 5 min. Also, the yields of extract achieved when using MAE for 20 min at 1340 W were significantly higher than those achieved at 336 and 670 W for the same time duration by 22.34 % and 33 %, respectively, while 336 and 670 W exhibited no statistical difference between each other. At 10 min, there was no statistical difference between the yields of the extracts obtained through the application of either of the 3 MW power levels. Overall, 20 min achieved the highest extract yields from *A. esculenta* at any MW power used. The highest extract yields of 73 % through MAE was obtained at the high power and time combination of 1340 W for 20 min, while the lowest was recorded for the low power and time combination of 336 W for 5 min, amounting to 27 %, supporting the fact that the higher the power and time of MW application, higher the increase in extract yields will be achieved. High MW power can create strong

Fig. 2. Impact of variable MW (336–1340 W), US (50–200 W) power and time (5–20 min) on the yields of extract achieved by (A) MAE (B) UAE and (C) UMAE. Results are expressed as average \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$). Different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) within the same extraction conditions (MAE, UAE and UMAE) at variable extraction times (lower case letters) or within the same extraction duration at variable technological treatments (upper case letters). In UMAE treatments, different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between the same UMAE conditions at different extraction times.

dielectric heating that can facilitate improved diffusion of cellular constituents into the extraction solvent [47].

The highest yields of extract using UAE were achieved by using medium power of 100 W for 5 min ($\approx 59\%$) as seen in Fig. 2B. These yields were significantly higher compared to those achieved by the other 2 US powers using the same treatment duration; and interestingly, higher than those achieved when using any of the US powers during prolonged US treatments of 10 and 20 min. This could indicate that extraction for 5 min at US power of 100 W was sufficient to obtain the maximum yield, as beyond these levels, saturation of the extraction solvent must have been attained, hindering further extract yield.

In the case of UMAE (Fig. 2C), a low MW power of 336 W and high US power of 200 W at a low extraction time of 5 min achieved the highest extract yields of $\approx 58\%$. These results are comparable to those achieved using UAE alone ($\approx 59\%$). Nevertheless, if we compare all the 3 different extraction methods, MAE provided extract yield that was nearly 1.25 times higher than that obtained by UAE or UMAE alone. There are limited studies reporting yields of extract from macroalgae using these innovative technologies. In a similar study, García-Vaquero, Ravindran, Walsh, O'Doherty, Jaiswal, Brijesh kumar and Rajauria [13] obtained the highest yields of extract using UMAE from *Fucus vesiculosus* (354.67 ± 2.33 mg dried extract/g) and *Pelvetia canaliculata* (240.33 ± 1.20 mg dried extract/g) compared to those achieved by UAE, MAE, hydrothermal-assisted extraction and high-pressure-assisted extraction.

3.2. Chemical composition of the extracts

3.2.1. TPC

While evaluating the impact of MAE alone on TPC (Fig. 3A) there were no significant differences on TPC between 336 W and 670 W, or between 670 W and 1340 W. At 670 W there was no significant

differences in the levels of TPC based on extraction time, while MAE at 1340 W applied for 10 min achieved approximately 25 % higher TPC compared to those achieved with 5 min of extraction, however, further time increase to 20 min resulted in a slight decrease of TPC. Overall, highest TPC of 1.82 ± 0.16 mg GAE/100 mg extract was achieved by MAE at 336 W and 5 min. UAE, on the other hand, had only small differences in TPC when explored at several US power and time combinations (Fig. 3B). There were no statistical differences between the levels of TPC achieved by increasing the time of extraction when using 50 or 200 W at the 3 extraction times. However, 20 min extraction at 100 W achieved the highest TPC of 1.47 ± 0.03 mg GAE/100 mg extract which was significantly higher than 5 and 10 min extraction at the same US power, while the lowest TPC of 0.99 ± 0.11 mg GAE/100 mg extract was achieved when using 100 W during 5 min. UMAE (Fig. 3C), overall, achieved the highest levels of TPC compared to MAE and UAE. The highest level of TPC (2.07 ± 0.04 mg GAE/100 mg extract) was achieved by UMAE at 50 W of US power, 1340 W of MW power and 10 min of extraction time. This TPC value is 13.73 % and 40.81 % higher than those maximum levels achieved by MAE and UAE, respectively; indicating the effectiveness of UMAE over UAE and MAE in harnessing TPC. In similar studies, García-Vaquero, Ravindran, Walsh, O'Doherty, Jaiswal, Brijesh kumar and Rajauria [13] reported that UAE (26 kHz of US frequency, 100 % US amplitude) using 50 % methanol achieved the highest yields of TPC compared to MAE, UMAE, high pressure assisted extraction and hydrothermal assisted extraction to recover TPC amounting to 445.0 ± 4.6 mg GAE/g from dried *F. vesiculosus* and 250.6 ± 6 mg GAE/g from dried *P. canaliculata*.

Overall, the TPC of all the extracts achieved in this study were quantitatively minimal in our study. Differences in sample processing can explain the low levels of TPC achieved in the current study. Similarly, a study extracting TPC from dried and powdered *Sargassum wightii*

Fig. 3. Impact of variable MW (336–1340 W), US (50–200 W) power and time (5–20 min) on the levels of TPC in extract achieved by (A) MAE (B) UAE and (C) UMAE. Results are expressed as average \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$). Different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) within the same extraction conditions (MAE, UAE and UMAE) at variable extraction times (lower case letters) or within the same extraction duration at variable technological treatments (upper case letters). In UMAE treatments, different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between the same UMAE conditions at different extraction times.

using UAE with methanol achieved approximately 14.5 mg GAE/g extract [48]. Dried macroalgae have more concentrated polyphenols when used as initial biomass for extraction compared with the current study using fresh biomass, which could account for higher extraction of polyphenols. Moreover, most literature reporting extraction of TPC from macroalgae used ethanol or methanol as the extraction solvent, while in the current study, the solvent of extraction of choice was ultrapure water, improving the sustainability of the extraction processes. However, water has lesser polarity than alcohols and, hence, has comparatively lesser affinity towards polyphenols, explaining thus, the low levels of TPC as compared to existing literature for other brown macroalgal species [15,49,50]. However, it has to be kept in mind that methanol is severely toxic and if traces of methanol remain in the extract, this reagent can be extremely dangerous if intended for food, feed, nutraceutical, or pharmaceutical applications. Similarly to the current study, Moreira, Chenlo, Sineiro, Arufe and Sexto [51] also reported low TPC values (0.5 g phloroglucinol equivalents (PGE)/L) in aqueous extracts obtained through UAE (US power: 80 W/cm², extraction time: 4 min) from dried *F. vesiculosus*. Gisbert, Sineiro and Moreira [52] compared salt water and distilled water as extraction solvents using UAE to extract phenolics from *A. nodosum*. The authors reported that UAE (power: 90 W/cm²; 15 min) with the saline solvent achieved lower TPC (2.84 ± 0.07 g PGE/L) than those extracted using water (3.08 ± 0.08 g PGE/L). Apart from these differences that could be explained by the variable processing and extraction parameters, environmental conditions of growth and the seasons in which they are harvested can also affect the amount of TPC in macroalgae which could have played a role in the results observed in our study.

3.2.2. Protein contents

When using MAE alone (seen in Fig. 4A), at the highest extraction time of 20 min, all the 3 MW power levels (336, 670 and 1340 W) achieved similar levels of protein in the extracts (4.19–4.66 mg BSAE/100 mg extract) with no statistical differences between them. This reflected that at an extended MW application time of 20 min, all MW power levels were efficient enough to extract substantial quantities of macroalgal proteins in water. However, MAE power of 1340 W at an extraction time of 10 min achieved the highest protein content among all the MAE extracts, amounting to 4.71 ± 0.2 mg BSAE/100 mg extract, nearly equal to the amount extracted at 20 min. This was significantly higher than the protein content observed in case of 5 min extraction at the same power level of 1340 W, but insignificantly different from that obtained at a higher extraction time of 20 min. It was also noted that, at 10 min extraction duration, 1340 W gave statistically higher protein content in the extract over 336 and 670 W, while the protein content obtained from the latter two power levels did not show any significant difference between each of them. This could be attributed to saturation of the solvent with the proteins after 10 min and at 1340 W, beyond which further extraction could not occur. So, applying a high MW power of 1340 W for a moderate duration of 10 min can be chosen as the optimal condition for protein recovery from the macroalgae.

In the case of UAE (Fig. 4B) US power of 200 W for 20 min yielded the highest protein content in the extract (4.34 ± 0.075 mg BSAE/100 mg extract). An increasing pattern in the protein content was observed in case of 100 W with increasing time from 5, 10 to 20 min. A similar pattern of increasing protein extraction yields with an increase in US irradiation time was also reported by Wang, Wang, Huang, Hayat, Kurtz, Wu, Ahmad and Zheng [53], who obtained the highest protein yields of 25.59 ± 1.14 % when US duration was prolonged from 5 to 15 min.

Fig. 4. Impact of variable MW (336–1340 W), US (50–200 W) power and time (5–20 min) on the levels of protein content in extracts achieved by (A) MAE (B) UAE and (C) UMAE. Results are expressed as average \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$). Different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) within the same extraction conditions (MAE, UAE and UMAE) at variable extraction times (lower case letters) or within the same extraction duration at variable technological treatments (upper case letters). In UMAE treatments, different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between the same UMAE conditions at different extraction times.

When comparing all the treatments used for 10 min, no statistical difference was observed between the 3 power levels. 5 min extraction yielded higher protein content at 200 W compared to that at 50 W. However, the minimum protein content of 1.75 ± 0.03 mg BSAE/100 mg extract was obtained at medium power and low time combination of 100 W and 5 min which is 1.36 and 1.30 fold lesser than the protein content obtained under the low extraction combinations of power and time of 50 W, 5 min as well as 50 W, 10 min, respectively. Higher US power could have possibly led to the formation of larger protein aggregates that took considerably longer time to diffuse in to the extraction solvent. This was reflected in the protein content achieving maximum only at 20 min at 200 W.

In the case of UMAE (Fig. 4C), the highest protein content of 15.62 ± 1.69 mg BSAE/100 mg extract was obtained at 1340 W of MW power and 100 W of US power applied for 20 min. This is nearly 3.3 and 3.6 folds higher than the highest protein contents achieved by MAE and UAE, respectively. Therefore, MAE, via its ability to improve diffusional mass transfer by dielectric heating of the polar molecules of water, and UAE, via its cavitation-induced shear forces that disintegrate the cell wall, creating pores and channels, were useful when combined during UMAE for the creation of disruptions of the macroalgal matrix resulting in increased protein extraction. Currently, there is limited comparable literature reporting protein extraction from brown seaweeds using ultrasound and/or microwave techniques. In a recent study by André, Flórez-Fernández, Domínguez and Torres [54], on application of microwave hydrothermal treatment (5 min at 850 W, 120 to 200 °C) to green seaweed, *Ulva* spp., resulting extracts demonstrated protein contents between 1 and 2 mg BSAE/100 g of liquid extract, which is lesser than that obtained in our study. Apart from the role of dual US and MW application in our study that could have yielded in higher protein in the

extract, analysis of the dried extract could have accounted for higher protein content unlike the analysis of protein in the liquid extract conducted by André, Flórez-Fernández, Domínguez and Torres [54]. Cheng, Shu, Chen, Dai, Wan, Chen and Dong [55] investigated the use of US (25 kHz, 300 W) integrated with MW (81 W) to extract proteins from *Moringa oleifera* leaves. They reported that the protein yield when combining both technologies reached 82.07 mg/g, which was higher than the yields achieved by conventional solvent-based extraction using Tris-HCl buffer solution without US and MW application, reaching 68.99 mg/g [55]. The simultaneous dual application of US and MW for protein extraction from biological plant-based matrices is scarcely investigated and our study is reportedly the first to explore the hybrid use of these 2 technologies for protein recovery from the brown seaweed *A. esculenta*.

3.2.3. TSC contents

When using MAE (Fig. 5A), the highest TSC achieved were ≈ 21 mg GE/100 mg extract at 670 W for 5 min, which was insignificantly different from the values obtained at 10 or 20 min at the same power, but significantly higher than 5 min extraction at higher power of 1340 W. This could potentially indicate that at the high MW power levels, the temperature of the reaction increased. Thus, TSC tends to degrade or form Maillard browning products. This was also mentioned by Saravana, Choi, Park, Woo and Chun [56], who observed a drop in glucose concentration on increasing the temperature and pressure during pressurized hot water extraction of *Saccharina japonica*. Rodrigues, Sousa, Silva, Amorim, Pereira, Rocha-Santos, Gomes, Duarte and Freitas [57] performed UAE using US bath in pulse mode for 60 min (ON time 10 min and OFF time 2 min) with water as a solvent, achieving extracts with 37.8 ± 0.16 mg GE/g extract.

The maximum levels of TSC of ≈ 33 mg GE/100 mg extract in the

Fig. 5. Impact of variable MW (336–1340 W), US (50–200 W) power and time (5–20 min) on the levels of TSC in extracts achieved by (A) MAE (B) UAE and (C) UMAE. Results are expressed as average \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$). Different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) within the same extraction conditions (MAE, UAE and UMAE) at variable extraction times (lower case letters) or within the same extraction duration at variable technological treatments (upper case letters). In UMAE treatments, different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between the same UMAE conditions at different extraction times.

current study were achieved by UAE at 200 W and 20 min (Fig. 5B), significantly higher than those achieved at 50 or 100 W using the same extraction times, as well as significantly higher than 5 and 10 min of extraction at 200 W. However, these results were similar to those of UMAE, reaching the highest TSC value of 30.44 ± 0.71 mg GE/100 mg extract at low MW power (336 W), medium US power (100 W) and minimum extraction time of 5 min (Fig. 5C). Hence, we can state that UMAE at lower time and power combinations, if not more but is equally efficient as UAE at higher power and time for extraction of TSC from *A. esculenta*. In a similar study, Garcia-Vaquero, Ummat, Tiwari and Rajauria [15] explored the extraction of TSC from dried *A. nodosum*. The authors achieved the maximum yield of TSC of 10.40 mg GE/100 mg macroalgae using UMAE (US amplitude: 100 %, MW power: 600 W, extraction time: 5 min). These TSC levels were higher compared to that achieved using MAE (1000 W, 5 min): 3.32 mg GE/100 mg dried macroalgae, and UAE (50 % US amplitude, 5 min): 2.57 mg GE/100 mg dried macroalgae. Borines, de Leon and Cuello [58] achieved reducing sugar yield of approximately 120 mg/g dried biomass from *Sargassum* spp. To achieve this yield, the authors used diluted sulfuric acid (3.4–4.6 % (w/v)) as a pre-treatment at 115 °C for 1.5 h followed by enzymatic hydrolysis using cellulase (50 FPU cellulase/g biomass) supplemented with β -glucosidase (250 CBU cellobiase/g biomass). In another study, by combining US (24 kHz, 200 W) with enzyme addition (Accellerase® 1500), Mapholi and Goosen [59] found that ultrasound-assisted enzymatic extraction of brown seaweed *Ecklonia maxima* outperformed both individual enzyme-assisted extraction and ultrasound-assisted extraction in total carbohydrate yield of the extract, resulting in its 20 % increase after 240 min.

Table 1

Profiling of organic acids (mg/g extract) of extracts from *A. esculenta*.

	MAE extracts		UAE extracts		UMAE extracts	
	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max
Succinic acid	7.52 \pm 0.2 a	6.94 \pm 0.03 b *	5.13 \pm 0.04 d	6.93 \pm 0.1 b *	6.09 \pm 0.2 c	5.79 \pm 0.07 c ^{ns}
Citric acid	1.15 \pm 0.01 d	1.62 \pm 0.03 c *	0.97 \pm 0.04 d	4.33 \pm 0.12 a *	2.54 \pm 0.36 b	0.40 \pm 0.01 e *
Lactic acid	39.08 \pm 1.02 a	36.04 \pm 0.07 ab *	26.84 \pm 0.3 c	36.04 \pm 0.54 ab *	30.24 \pm 4.92 c	30.47 \pm 0.75 bc ^{ns}
Malic acid	1.36 \pm 0.04 d	2.05 \pm 0.13 c *	1.24 \pm 0.03 d	2.42 \pm 0.02 b *	3.02 \pm 0.11 a	0.89 \pm 0.02 e *
Pyruvic acid	8.04 \pm 0.11 d	11.36 \pm 0.22 c *	6.71 \pm 0.13 d	30.39 \pm 0.88 a *	18.32 \pm 1.04 b	2.73 \pm 0.03 e *
α -Ketoglutaric acid	0.64 \pm 0.01 e	1.13 \pm 0.01 c *	0.65 \pm 0.01 de	1.96 \pm 0.02 b *	2.41 \pm 0.03 a	0.69 \pm 0.01 d *

Values in the table are expressed as average \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$). Different letters indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the value of each organic acid between all treatments in each row. The differences within each extraction treatment between “min” and “max” are indicated as * $p < 0.05$ and ^{ns}non-significant. Abbreviations “min” and “max” refer to the extraction conditions achieving minimum and maximum TSC. These conditions were for MAE (min: 1340 W/20 min; max: 670 W/5 min), for UAE (min: 100 W/5 min, max: 200 W/20 min); and for UMAE (min: 670 W (MW)/100 W (US)/5 min, max: 336 W (MW)/100 W (US)/5 min).

3.2.4. Organic acids

Organic acids from marine biomass hold immense value, having great market potential and applications in food, fine chemical and pharmaceutical fields [60]. As previously highlighted, based on the hypothesis of co-extraction of TSC with organic acids, selected samples achieving the highest (Max) and lowest (Min) levels of TSC were further analysed for their content of organic acids (see Table 1).

Overall, lactic acid followed by pyruvic acid were the major organic acids present in *A. esculenta* extracts, while minimum amounts of α -ketoglutaric and citric acids were also present. When analysing the influence of the different extraction technologies on the profile of organic acids, UAE (200 W, 20 min) achieved the highest concentrations of citric acid (4.33 %) and pyruvic acid (30.4 %) among all the extracts analysed. UMAE (670 W (MW), 100 W (US), 5 min) achieved extracts with the highest amount of malic and α -ketoglutaric acids. In the case of succinic and lactic acids, these compounds were the highest in MAE extracts (1340 W, 20 min). Several studies on the production of organic acids by microbial fermentation of algal biomass have been reported [61–63]. Bach, Tran and Lystad [64] also reported higher concentrations of lactic acid (~130 mg/L) over succinic acid (~35 mg/L) in the water-soluble fraction obtained through hydrothermal liquefaction of sugar kelp. High concentrations of lactic acid in our extracts could conceivably be linked to its fermentative production by the naturally present halophilic and halo-tolerant bacteria in the fresh algal biomass [65]. To our knowledge, this is the first study reporting the influence of various innovative technological treatments of macroalgae on the aqueous extraction of organic acids from *A. esculenta* or any other macroalgal species.

3.3. Influence of extraction technologies on antioxidant properties

3.3.1. FRAP and DPPH radical scavenging activity

Among the antioxidant activity assays conducted, the FRAP value (Fig. 6) was at its highest ($38.36 \pm 3.36 \mu\text{M TE/mg extract}$) in the extract of UMAE (1340 W (MW), 50 W (US), 10 min) which also achieved the highest TPC value. The FRAP value appreciated in the UMAE extract was higher than the maximum values of FRAP achieved by MAE and UAE conditions by 2.5 and 3.22 folds, respectively. Similarly, UMAE (670 W (MW), 50 W (US) and 5 min) had the highest DPPH radical scavenging activity ($92.38 \pm 0.44 \%$), exceeding the maximum values obtained through MAE and UAE by 1.23 and 1.37 folds, respectively (Fig. 7).

In similar studies by García-Vaquero, Ravindran, Walsh, O'Doherty, Jaiswal, Brijesh kumar and Rajauria [13], the maximum antioxidant activity determined as DPPH radical scavenging activity was achieved in extracts generated by UAE and UMAE in ethanol/water solution (50 % v/v), of approximately 110 mM TE/g in *F. vesiculosus* and 94 mM TE/g in *P. canaliculata*. In the case of FRAP, *P. canaliculata* extracts produced by UAE exhibited the highest FRAP values ($80 \pm 3 \text{ mM TE/g}$), with no proper pattern followed by the extraction technologies in the case of *F. vesiculosus* [13]. Goksen [66] also explored UAE at 10 % amplitude for 15 min in ethanol/water solution (80 % v/v) to achieve extracts with high antioxidant activity determined by DPPH ($105.69 \pm 3.02 \mu\text{mol TE/100 g}$) from *Laurencia papillosa*. Microwave-assisted pressurized hot water extraction of dried brown seaweed *Rugulopteryx okamurae* by Ferreira-Anta, Flórez-Fernández, Torres, Mazón and Dominguez [67] led to a maximum of nearly 32 % DPPH radical scavenging activity in the extract which is comparatively lot lesser than the maximum obtained in our study (92.38 %) through UMAE, thereby validating the better efficacy of combined US and MW application.

Fig. 6. Impact of variable MW (336–1340 W), US (50–200 W) power and time (5–20 min) on the levels of FRAP in extracts achieved by (A) MAE (B) UAE and (C) UMAE. Results are expressed as average \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$). Different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) within the same extraction conditions (MAE, UAE and UMAE) at variable extraction times (lower case letters) or within the same extraction duration at variable technological treatments (upper case letters). In UMAE treatments, different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between the same UMAE conditions at different extraction times.

Fig. 7. Impact of variable MW (336–1340 W), US (50–200 W) power and time (5–20 min) on the levels of DPPH in extracts achieved by (A) MAE (B) UAE, and (C) UMAE. Results are expressed as average \pm standard error of the mean ($n = 6$). Different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) within the same extraction conditions (MAE, UAE, and UMAE) at variable extraction times (lower case letters) or within the same extraction duration at variable technological treatments (upper case letters). In UMAE treatments, different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between the same UMAE conditions at different extraction times.

3.4. Correlation and principal component analysis

Both DPPH and FRAP of the extracts of this study were positively and strongly correlated with TPC as seen in Fig. 8. These results were also appreciated by Goksen [66] who recorded a concomitant rise in antioxidant activities (both DPPH and FRAP), with total phenolic content in the extracts obtained on UAE from the macroalgae, *Laurencia papillosa*. Moreover, proteins also seem to be correlated to FRAP activity. Thereby, peptides from macroalgae have been cited previously in literature to demonstrate antioxidant activities [68] and this could be one of the reason behind the positive correlation between protein content and FRAP activity. Interestingly, the TSC levels of the extracts seem to be negatively correlated with their antioxidant activity. A similar negative correlation between antioxidant activity (DPPH, FRAP) and total soluble sugar content was also reported by Garcia-Vaquero, Rajauria, Miranda, Sweeney, Lopez-Alonso and O'Doherty [69], in the brown macroalgae, *A. nodosum*.

A principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to obtain an overview of the similarities and differences in the composition and antioxidant activity of the extracts together with the US, MW and time of extraction used with the different technological treatments (see Fig. 9). Principal component 1 (PC1) explained 32.91 % of the variation of the data set and PC2 explained 17.67 %. The PC1 separates the yields and TSC, which seem to group together with US processing conditions. Reports identifying the strong influence of US power in producing higher yields of extracts and extracting considerable amounts of soluble sugars from various biological matrices exist in previous literature [70–72]. The PC2 further separates the variation of the data set by clustering the antioxidant activities with TPC, as seen also previously in the correlation analysis. MW power, time and protein were found to be clustered

together by PC1, indicating the close association of MW power and processing time on protein extraction, as highlighted in numerous studies [73,74].

3.5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

SEM images at a magnification of 1000 \times and a spatial resolution of 5 μm were analysed to comprehend the physical impact of the three technological interventions on the surface morphology of the macroalgal biomass that could explain the leaching of compounds and enhance the extraction. The biomass residues processed after MAE (1340 W, 10 min), UAE (200 W, 20 min) and UMAE (US power: 100 W; MW power: 1340 W; 20 min) were selected for the SEM evaluation along with the untreated fresh biomass as control.

As observed in Fig. 10A, the surface of the fresh untreated *A. esculenta* looks fairly smooth with very few undulations that could arise from the inherent wavy and lacinate surface of the seaweed fronds. Fig. 10B represents the MAE residue which is observed to be severely rough and irregular with certain tubular structures that appear to have formed after dislodging due to the damage induced by the technological treatment. As seen in Fig. 10C, UAE residue also appears to be severely coarse and jagged with numerous pores and tiny pits that appear to have been formed on the surface due to cavitation-induced sonoporation. UMAE residue (see Fig. 10D), likewise can be visualized to be particularly damaged with enlarged pore formation on the macroalgal surface brought about by the combined force of US and MW radiations. Formation of pores and a rough surface suggest significant mutilation of the treated biomass, resulting in better infiltration of extraction solvent into the macroalgal cell to leach out the target compounds. This validates the results demonstrating superior recovery of

Fig. 8. Correlation matrices of the composition and antioxidant parameters in extracts achieved from *A. esculenta*. The sign of the correlations is indicated by the colour (negative: red; positive: blue) and the depth of the colours and size of the square indicates the strength of the correlations (0–1). Abbreviations in the figure are as follows: TPC (total phenolic content), TSC (total soluble carbohydrates), DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical scavenging activity), FRAP (Ferric reducing antioxidant power), US (ultrasound), and MW (microwave). The statistical significance of the correlations is indicated in the figure as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

phytochemicals through MAE, UAE and majorly through UMAE. Garcia-Vaquero, Ummat, Tiwari and Rajauria [15] carried out similar imaging studies on dried *A. nodosum* biomass and reported significant damage to macroalgal cuticle by simultaneous US and MW application during the

recovery of carbohydrates and phenolic compounds, while Wang, Xu, Wang, Gao, Fu and Zhao [75] reports similar surface modification of *Laminaria* sp. by sequential application of MW, US and enzyme while extracting iodine amino acids. Likewise, Mateluna, Figueroa, Ortiz and Aguilera [76] found that ultrasound processing at 20 kHz of the seaweed, *Durvillaea antarctica* caused partial breakdown of the intermediate medullary zone of the algal tissue.

4. Conclusions

MAE, UAE and UMAE contributed to the favourable extraction of different phytochemicals, organic acids and antioxidant properties under different conditions of power and treatment time from fresh *A. esculenta*. MAE treatments achieved overall, the highest extraction yield (73 %) and extracts containing the highest levels of succinic (7.52 mg/g extract) and lactic acids (39.08 mg/g extract). On the other hand, UAE generated extracts have high levels of TSC (33 mg GE/100 mg extract), and citric (4.33 mg/g extract) and pyruvic acids (30.39 mg/g extract). UMAE favoured the extraction of TPC (2.07 mg GAE/100 mg extract) and recovered the extracts with the highest protein (15.62 mg protein/100 mg extract) and antioxidant activities (FRAP (38.36 μ M TE/mg extract) and 92.38 % DPPH radical scavenging activity). UMAE also contained the highest levels of malic (3.02 mg/g extract) and α -ketoglutaric acids (2.41 mg/g extract). The physical disruption of the macroalgal tissues by the technological treatments was also illustrated through the SEM images. The use of water as the extraction solvent is particularly advantageous due to its safety, cost-effectiveness, and environmental friendliness. Further studies exploring the bioactivity of the extracts, either *in-vitro* or *in-vivo*, are crucial to unlock the full potential of these extracts for applications in pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals, and functional foods. *In-vitro* investigations are already underway to evaluate the antimicrobial potential of selected extracts from this study. Continued refinement and optimization of extraction methodologies, combined with energy consumption assessment and cost analysis, will enable their scale-up to industry levels. The results of this study will contribute to support the adoption of sustainable and efficient technologies in the algal sector for extracting valuable bioactive compounds and

Fig. 9. The principal component analysis scatter plot representing the scores of the composition of the extracts and their processing parameters. Abbreviations in the figure are as follows: TPC (total phenolic content), TSC (total soluble carbohydrates), DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical scavenging activity), FRAP (Ferric reducing antioxidant power), US (ultrasound), and MW (microwave).

Fig. 10. SEM images of *A. esculenta* (A) untreated and the residual biomass following, (B) MAE (1340 W, 10 min), (C) UAE (200 W, 20 min), and (D) UMAE (US power: 100 W; MW power: 1340 W; 20 min). Scale bars in each figure represent 5 µm.

underexplored organic acids. This represents a significant milestone to unlock the future use of these compounds, expanding the potential applications of macroalgal molecules for multiple purposes in the food, pharmaceutical and cosmeceutical industries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Rahel Suchintita Das: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Brijesh K. Tiwari:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Serkan Selli:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Hasim Kelebek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Marco Garcia-Vaquero:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2025.103896>.

Data availability

All data used is specified within the manuscript.

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